

Epidemiology of Urinary Schistosomiasis amongst Primary School Children in Amiri, Oru East Local Government Area

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ABSTRACT:

The study evaluated the epidemiology of Schistosomiasis Haematobia among Primary School Children of Amiri, Oru East Local Government Area, Imo state. A total of three primary schools with 133 pupils were used for this study, comprising of 59 boys and 74 girls respectively. Samples of urine were collected and subjected to urine analysis. Prevalence rate of *Schistosoma haematobium* infection in the community was (1.5%). Findings from this study revealed that of the three primary schools investigated, only Central Primary School, Ubahaze recorded 2 (53.3%) of *S. haematobium* infection. Of 59 male pupils investigated, only 2(3.39%) of them had urinary Schistosomiasis while none was found among 74 female pupils that were tested. No urinary schistosomiasis was recorded in all pupils of primary 1-5 while only two pupils out of 30 (6.67%) of primary 6 had this parasitic infection. In the investigation, *Schistosomiasis haematobia* infections were recorded among pupils that are above 12 years in age which include 2(5.71%) pupils. Two pupils (11.11%) who drink from the stream/river and two (9.52%) pupils who swim in the river sometimes and sometimes wash themselves in the river out of 21 recorded *S. haematobium* infection. The effect of deworming on the infection rate of *S. haematobium* in primary school children indicate that 1 (4.17%) children who had been dewormed between 4 and 6 months ago have a positive result for *S. haematobium* infections and 1 (2.27%) children who had been dewormed more than six months ago were also positive to the disease. It can thus be concluded, from the results obtained, that not many primary school children in Amiri, Oru East LGA suffer from schistosomiasis and that male children are at higher risk of developing the disease than female children. Based on the research findings, it is recommended that praziquantel treatment interventions as well as education for the community should be put in place to prevent schistosomiasis. The findings suggest that urinary schistosomiasis is hypopendemic in the study area, although water-contact activities remain important risk factors for infection.

Keywords: *Urinary schistosomiasis, Schistosoma haematobium, epidemiology, school children, Nigeria, neglected tropical disease*

INTRODUCTION:

It is important to understand that schistosomiasis is one of the leading Neglected Tropical Diseases (NTDs), with about 240 million people infected worldwide, and an additional 700 million are at risk (Brunn and Aagaard-Hansen, 2008). Schistosomiasis is primarily an occupational disease of farmers, fishermen, and irrigation farms' workers. In addition to being an occupational disease, other causes of the high prevalence of urinary schistosomiasis in the developing countries include inadequate sanitary conditions, poverty, ignorance, lack of access to healthcare centers and other social amenities (WHO, 2017). It is known that sub-Saharan Africa accounts for more than 90 percent of the 240 million cases

of human schistosomiasis estimated in the world and has a record of over 200,000 schistosomiasis-related deaths yearly (Hotez and Kamath, 2009). It is estimated that Nigeria has a very high prevalence rate for the disease, where about 29 million individuals are infected and approximately 101 million Nigerians at risk of contracting the disease in the year 2010 (Hotez and Kamath, 2009; Hotez et al., 2012; WHO,2022). The human gets infected through contact with water contaminated with the free-swimming cercariae, which can easily penetrate their skin (Wright, 1988). The availability of intermediate snail hosts of the parasite and the increase in contact of humans with infected water sources are the primary determinants that encourage the

spread of this disease. The individuals most susceptible to developing this infection include those living or visiting endemic areas and making contact with water sources harboring the intermediate host.⁸ Children become victims of urinary schistosomiasis owing to their tendency to play in water that puts them at greater risk of developing the infection (WHO, 2017). In endemic regions such as Nigeria, the most common symptom exhibited by children is microscopic hematuria as a sign of pathological effects on the lower urinary tract due to continuous exposure and re-infection. Long-standing untreated infections cause polyps, hypertrophic nodule formations, and egg deposition resulting in development of granulomas, fibrosis, and calcification of the bladder wall (Barsoum et al., 2013). With aging, vesicoureteral reflux, and obstructive uropathy becomes more likely and children end up suffering from complications such as hydronephrosis, chronic bacteriuria, vesical cancer, and occasionally renal failure in their younger years (Badmos et al., 2009; Khalaf et al., 2012). The use of school-age children as participants in the study of urinary schistosomiasis is appropriate for several reasons. School-age children are well-known to have bad hygienic practices and love playing in water, thus making them susceptible to infections. It can be seen that information derived from such age groups has been helpful not only to justify their inclusion in mass drug administration programs but also to show the necessity of carrying out such programs (WHO, 2017; 2012). Despite several studies on urinary schistosomiasis in different parts of Nigeria, there is limited epidemiological information regarding the infection among school children in Amiri community, Imo State. There has been a problem with urinary schistosomiasis in some parts of Imo State, south-eastern Nigeria (Uneke et al., 2006). To come up with current guidelines for effective prevention and control measures, the current study examines the epidemiology of the disease among primary school children in Amiri, Oru East, Imo State.

General Objective:

To assess the epidemiology of urinary schistosomiasis among primary school children in Amiri community.

Specific Objectives:

1. To determine the prevalence of *Schistosoma haematobium* infection among school children.
2. To assess age and sex-related distribution of infection.
3. To evaluate water-contact risk factors associated with infection.
4. To determine the effect of deworming practices on infection rate.

Study Area:

Amiri is a town in Oru-East a Local Government Area of Imo State, Nigeria. Its headquarters is at Omuma. The following are towns that make up Oru East: Akatta, Akuma, Amagu, Amiri, Awo-Omamma, and Omuma. Oru East is bounded by Njaba LGA, Mbaitolu, Orlu, Oguta, Orsu and Oru west Local Government Area. Occupationally, the people of the state are mainly small scale farmers, civil servants, business men and women, traders and artisans. It generally has sandy/Loamy soil and in some areas it may be clay or muddy soil. Education is the biggest industry in Imo State, which is the reason why there are so many schools in the study-comprising of primary, secondary and tertiary institution. The area is characterized by tropical rainfall and presence of rivers and streams which may support transmission of schistosomiasis.

Ethical Clearance:

Ethical clearance and permission was obtained from the Post Graduate Research Board of Animal and Environmental Department of Imo State University, Owerri, Nigeria. Consent was sought and obtained from the authorities of the community and L.G.A, followed by mobilization of the school children through their Headmistress

Study Population:

The study populations included all the pupils male and female, aged <6 and ≥ 12 from Community Primary School Ugbeke, Mbubu Progressive Primary School Mbubu, and central Primary School, Ubahaze. And a total of 133 pupils were selected from the three schools. Only pupils whose parents/guardians consented were included in the study, while pupils who declined participation were excluded.

Sample Collection/Microscopy:

A mid-stream sample of urine was obtained from 200 randomly selected students across 3 schools. Sample collection was done using a clean plastic container from 10.00am – 12.00 pm. This period was important because the eggs were shed from 10.00 am – 12.00 pm. Proper labelling was carried out by labeling the plastics with the following information; name, sex, age, school, and laboratory number. Preservation of the samples was done using an ice block to avoid the hatching of ova of *Schistosoma haematobium* during transportation. Observation of the specimens for haematuria (blood in urine) was done prior to transportation to the laboratory where analysis was done within two hours of sampling. Examination of the urine samples in the laboratory of animal and environmental biology, Imo state university. 10mls of each urine sample was thoroughly mixed, and centrifuged at 300 revolutions per minute (rpm) for 3

minutes. The supernatant was discarded, and the deposited substances were examined using 10X and 40X objective of light microscope. Urine samples that contained egg(s) of *Schistosoma haematobium* and those with no eggs were recorded.

Statistical analysis:

Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics and Chi-square analysis at $p < 0.05$.

RESULTS:

A total of 300 pupils were designed to be sampled in this study but only 133 consented to participate. Of this number, 2(1.50%) of them were positive for *S.haematobium* infection (Table 1). There was significant difference ($P < 0.05$) in school related *S.haematobium* infection rate as well as the 2 cases of infection were observed among pupil from central primary school, ubahaze. There was no *S.haematobium* infection observed among the pupils sampled from community primary school, ugbeke and mbubu progressive primary school, mbubu. On a further discussion of the two positive pupils, they said that they had visited their maternal homes (a nearby community) severally. They also enjoyed swimming in the Njaba river. Sex and age -related infection rate of urinary schistosomiasis among school pupils in Amiri (table 2) shows that a total of 133 school children from Amiri took part in the study. Of this number, 59 were male, while the remaining 74 were female pupils. There was significant difference ($P < 0.05$) in the sex related infection rate of *S.haematobium* as all the positive cases were the male pupils. Chi-square analysis of the result showed that there was significant difference ($P < 0.05$) in age-related *S.haematobium* infection rate in the school samples as all the 2 cases of infection were recorded amongst children aged ≥ 12 years old. The class-related infection rate of urinary schistosomiasis among school pupils of Amiri (table 3) showed that there was significant difference ($P < 0.05$) in the class related infection rate of *S.haematobium* infection

in the schools sampled. All the 2 cases infection were recorded in primary six. The effect of sources of drinking water on the infection rate of *S.haematobium* among primary school children (table 4) showed that the sources of drinking water by the school pupils varied significantly as great majority of them (53.38%) indicated that borehole was their main source. The least source of drinking water was underground tank (6.02%). All the 2 cases of *S.haematobium* were recorded amongst the group whose source were stream/river (Table 5). So, the sources of drinking water had significant effect ($P < 0.05$) on the infection rate of *S.haematobium* among primary school children in amiri. The effect of the frequency of swimming in rivers on the infection rate of *S.haematobium* among primary school children (table 5) showed that of all the children sampled, (54.21%) had not experienced swimming in river, and only (5.79%) indicated that they had swam sometimes in the river. All the 2 cases of *S.haematobium* infection were recorded among the pupils who had sometimes swam in the river. The effect of the frequency of washing laundry in the river on the infection rate of *S. haematobium* among primary school children (table 6) showed that frequency of washing laundry in the river on the infection rate of *S.haematobium* among primary school children on the study area, as high as 125(53.98%) of them never washed laundry in any river. Only 8(6.02%) of them had sometimes washed laundry in rivers. None indicated that they had regular contact with water during laundry. Frequency of washing laundry in the river on the infection rate of *S.haematobium* among primary school children were significant ($P < 0.05$) as the 2 cases of infection were among the pupils who sometimes washed laundry in rivers. The effect of deworming on the infection rate of *S. haematobium* among primary school children (tale 7) showed that Chi-square analysis of the result showed that deworming had significant effect ($P < 0.05$) On the prevalence of *S. haematobium* infection among the school pupils to the extent that the 2 positive cases were recorded amongst children who had their last deworming drugs 4-6 months and more than six months ago.

Table 1: School-related prevalence of urinary schistosomiasis among school pupils

Name of schools	No examined	No positive	Percentage (%)
Community Primary School Ugbeke	25	0	0.00%
Mbubu Progressive Primary School	47	0	0.00%
Central Primary School, Ubahaze	61	2	3.28%
Total	133	2	1.50%

Table 2; Sex and Age related prevalence of urinary schistosomiasis among school pupils

Variables	No examined	No positive	Percentage (%)
Sex			
Male	59	2	3.39
Female	74	0	0.00
Total	133	2	1.50%

Age			
<6	16	0	0.00
6-7	22	0	0.00
8-9	28	0	0.00
10-11	32	0	0.00
≥ 12	35	2	5.71
Total	133	2	1.50%

Table 3. Class-related infection rate of urinary schistosomiasis among school pupils

Class	No examined	No positive	Percentage (%)
Primary 1	18	0	0.0
Primary 2	18	0	0.0
Primary 3	19	0	0.0
Primary 4	20	0	0.0
Primary 5	28	0	0.0
Primary 6	30	2	6.67
Total	133	2	1.50

Table 4: The effect of sources of drinking water on the infection rate of *S.haematobium* among primary school children

source of drinking water	No examined	No positive	Percentage (%)
Stream/river	18	2	11.11
Bore hole	71	0	0.0
Iterant vendor	15	0	0.0
Underground tank	8	0	0.0
Others	21	0	0.0
Total	133	2	1.50

Table 5: The effect of the frequency of swimming in rivers on the infection rate of *S. haematobium* among primary school children

Frequency of swimming in river	No examined	No positive	Percentage (%)
Not at all	112	0	0.00
Sometimes	21	2	9.52
Regularly	0	0	0.00
Total	133	2	1.50

Table 6. The effect of the frequency of washing laundry in the river on the infection rate of *S. haematobium* among primary school children

Frequency of swimming in river	No examined	No positive	Percentage (%)
Not at all	125	0	0.00
Sometimes	8	2	25.0
Regularly	0	0	0.00
Total	133	2	1.50

Table 7: The effect of deworming exercise on the infection rate of *S.haematobium* among primary school children

Deworming exercise	No examined	No positive	Percentage (%)
Have not taken deworming drug before	0	0	0.00
I month ago	28	0	0.00
2-3 months ago	37	0	0.00

4-6 months ago	24	1	4.17
>6 months ago	44	1	2.27
Total	133	2	1.50

DISCUSSION:

Based on WHO classification, the prevalence observed in this study indicates a hypoendemic transmission pattern. The findings of the study on the epidemiology of urinary schistosomiasis in primary school pupils in Amiri, Oru-East Local Government Area of Imo state revealed that the infection is hypoendemic in this part of Imo State. Out of the three schools investigated, only Central Primary School, Ubahaze recorded 2 (53.3%) *S. haematobium*. This finding is also in agreement with results gotten from different parts of Nigeria. Nwosu et al. (2015), in their study: Prevalence of urinary schistosomiasis infection among primary school pupils in Ezza-North Local Government Area of Ebonyi State also found prevalence of *Schistosoma haematobius* infection as high as 17.5%. Also, in another study carried out by Mbata et al. (2009), the prevalence of urinary schistosomiasis infection was found to be up to 45.6% in Ogbadibo Local Government Area, Benue State, Nigeria. In this study, out of 59 male pupils examined, only 2 (3.39%) pupils were infected with urinary schistosomiasis. There was no case of urinary schistosomiasis in 74 female pupils examined. Although Ejima and Odaibo (2007) reported higher infection among girls, Nnoruka et al. (2000) suggested that there is no consistent pattern attributable to sex differences with respect to infection in Nigeria. In this study, urinary schistosomiasis was found in pupils 12 years or more than 2(5.71%). This finding agrees with the finding of Dakul et al. (2001) who reported the highest prevalence 65.8% among the age group 10-14years in Lankaku-Namu district, Quan'an-Pan LGA Plateau State. Sarkinfada et al. (2009) reported the highest prevalence of 57.4% in age group 10-14 in Danjarima community, Kumbotso LGA Kano State. The class-related infection rate of urinary schistosomiasis among school pupils of Amiri shows that no urinary schistosomiasis was found in all the pupils in primary 1-5. Only two persons in primary 6 (6.67%) had urinary schistosomiasis. In this study, urinary schistosomiasis was found in pupils 12 years or more than 2(5.71%). This finding agrees with the finding of Dakul et al. (2001) who reported the highest prevalence 65.8% among the age group 10-14years in Lankaku-Namu district, Quan'an-Pan LGA Plateau State. Sarkinfada et al. (2009) reported the highest prevalence of 57.4% in age group 10-14 in Danjarima community, Kumbotso LGA Kano State. Two pupils (11.11%) whose source of drinking water is stream/river were found positive for *S. haematobium*. Others were negative. This could be attributed to the fact

that the transmission cycle of *S. haematobium* requires contamination of surface water by excreta or urine and fresh water snail as an intermediate host and human water contact. The effect of the frequency of swimming in rivers on the infection rate of *S. haematobium* among primary school children in Amiri, Oru East LGA shows that 2 (9.52%) pupils out of 21 who swims sometime in the river tested positive for *S. haematobium*. This could be attributed to the fact that protracted water-contact activities, such as swimming, allow the penetration of infectious cercaria into a human host. Swimming was practiced more than other activities among the pupils and became the major form of transmission. The effect of the frequency of washing laundry in the river on the infection rate of *S. haematobium* among primary school children in Amiri, Oru East LGA shows that 2 (25%) pupils out of 8 who washes sometimes in the river tested positive for *S. haematobium*. This agrees with the finding of Okoli and Odaibo (1999) in a previous study that attributed higher infection rates of urinary schistosomiasis amongst school boys in Ibadan to a greater involvement in outdoor activities, such as swimming, washing, paddling of canoes, and irrigation. The effect of deworming on the infection rate of *S. haematobium* among primary school children in Amiri, Oru East LGA shows that 1 (4.17%) dewormed 4-6months ago tested positive to *S. haematobium* while 1 (2.27%) who dewormed more than 6 months ago also tested positive to *S. haematobium*.

Limitations of the Study:

The study was limited by small sample size and reliance on a single urine sample per participant, which may underestimate the true prevalence of infection.

Recommendations:

Regular school-based screening and praziquantel administration should be encouraged in endemic communities. Health education programs aimed at reducing risky water-contact activities among children should also be implemented.

CONCLUSION:

It can therefore be concluded, based on the obtained result that, only few number of primary school children in Amiri, Oru East LGA suffers the urinary schistosomiasis and that males are at higher risk of the diseases than females in the study area. It is recommended, based on the study that, administration of praziquantel appropriate interventions and health education for the communities

are required for the control and prevention of urinary schistosomiasis and its attendant illnesses in the area

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST:

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT:

The data used for this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

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